

**THEORETICAL STUDY OF GAS DYNAMIC AND THERMAL PROCESSES OCCURRING DURING
PLASMA ARC CUTTING WITH REVERSE POLARITY**

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ABSTRACT

The work is devoted to the numerical modeling of gas-dynamic and thermal processes during plasma-arc cutting of metals at reverse polarity using air as a plasma-forming gas. Using the developed mathematical model of thermal, gas-dynamic and electromagnetic processes in electric arc plasma generated by cutting plasma torches with reverse polarity, the main characteristics of the arc plasma flow inside the working channel of the plasma torch, in the open area of the arc and in the cutting cavity are determined. It has been established that the characteristics of the arc plasma under study are significantly influenced by the radius of the plasma torch output nozzle, the thickness of the product being cut, as well as the parameters of the plasma torch operating mode (current strength and gas flow). The transverse dimensions of the cutting cavity depend on the distance separating the cut of the plasma torch from the surface of the product being cut, the radius of the output nozzle of the plasma torch and the parameters of its operating mode.

Keywords: plasma arc cutting, reverse polarity, air, modeling, plasma flow characteristics, cut cavity dimensions.

The development of plasma-arc processes for processing materials using reverse polarity plasma torches is associated with their wide capabilities for cutting metals of large (up to 200 mm) thicknesses using air as a plasma-forming gas [1]. For a sufficiently detailed study of the features of this method of plasma-arc cutting, it is necessary to conduct a deep and comprehensive study of the physical processes occurring both in such plasma torches and in the material being processed [2]. In particular, the gas-dynamic, thermal and electrical characteristics of the arc plasma generated by such plasma torches have a great influence on the productivity, stability, as well as the resulting quality indicators of plasma-arc processes for processing materials [3]. At the same time, due to the complexity and diversity of these processes, mathematical modeling methods play a great role in conducting research aimed at improving the designs of plasma torches and choosing the optimal modes of their operation [4]. Therefore, the relevance of this work lies in the creation of a mathematical model of arc plasma generated by plasma torches at reverse polarity for further modeling of the behavior of arc plasma during plasma cutting at reverse polarity, as well as for performing numerical experiments on this type of metal cutting.

The purpose of the work is to perform numerical modeling of gas-dynamic and thermal processes occurring during plasma-arc cutting of metals at reverse polarity using air as a plasma-forming gas, to determine

the main characteristics of the plasma flow and the parameters of the cut formed with its help.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were solved:

1. Development of a mathematical model of arc plasma generated by plasmatrons at reverse polarity using air as a plasma-forming gas.
2. Modeling of gas-dynamic and thermal characteristics of a plasma flow.
3. Modeling the dimensions of the resulting cutting cavity.

When calculating the plasma flow generated by a cutting plasmatron with reverse polarity with a hollow anode, the geometric parameters of the plasmatron (internal dimensions of the hollow anode, swirler, output nozzle) were set based on its actual dimensions, namely (Fig. 1): $R_e = 2$ mm, $Z_4 = -8$ mm, $Z_3 = -13$ mm, $Z_2 = -17$ mm, $Z_1 = -18,5$ mm, $Z_A = -58,5$ mm, $R_A = 7$ mm.

The distance Z_{c1} to the cut product was assumed to be 9 mm, the thickness of the cut product was $Z_{c2} - Z_{c1} = 70$ mm. It was assumed that the area Z_C of cathode binding of the arc is located on the side of the product opposite from the plasma torch, i.e. $Z_C = Z_{c2}$, and the cutting cavity (

Here \underline{T} is the average plasma temperature; $\bar{v} = (\rho v + \rho' v') / \rho$, where v is the averaged radial velocity, ρ is the averaged plasma density, ρ' and v' are density and radial velocity pulsations; u is the averaged axial plasma velocity; W – averaged azimuthal rotation speed; p – pressure; C_p is the specific heat capacity of plasma at constant pressure; σ – specific electrical conductivity of plasma; j – electric current density vector; ψ – volumetric power density of self-radiation; $\bar{\eta}$ and $\bar{\chi}$ are the total coefficients of dynamic viscosity and thermal conductivity of the plasma, which are the sums of molecular and turbulent viscosity and thermal conductivity, respectively; μ_0 – universal magnetic constant; H_ϕ – azimuthal component of the magnetic field of the arc current.

The azimuthal component of the magnetic field of the arc current is related to the axial component of the electric field E_z strength by the relation

$$H_\phi = \frac{1}{r} E_z \int_0^r \sigma r dr. \quad (5)$$

When using the boundary layer approximation, the description of the distributed electromagnetic characteristics of the arc is carried out under the condition

$$p = p_{ext} - \int_z^0 \frac{dp_c}{dz} dz + \mu_0 E_z \int_r^{R_c(z)} \sigma H_\phi dr - \int_r^{R_c(z)} \rho \frac{W^2}{r} dr, \quad (7)$$

where p_{ext} is the pressure in the external environment. Here and further we assume that the section $z=0$ coincides with the cut of the plasmatron nozzle and the region $z \leq 0$ corresponds to the plasma flow in the working channel of the plasmatron, and the region $z > 0$ corresponds to the plasma flow behind the cut of the plasmatron nozzle. The gas-static pressure gradient dp_c/dz in the boundary layer approximation is also constant over the channel cross-section [6] and is determined from the condition of maintaining the total mass flow rate of the plasma-forming gas:

$$\rho_0 G = 2\pi \int_0^{R_c(z)} \rho u r dr, \quad (8)$$

where ρ_0 is the gas mass density under normal conditions, G is the gas volumetric flow rate. In the open section of the discharge ($z > 0$), the pressure is determined by the expression:

$$p = p_{ext} + \mu_0 E_z \int_r^{R_c(z)} \sigma H_\phi dr - \int_r^{R_c(z)} \rho \frac{W^2}{r} dr. \quad (9)$$

The system of equations (1) – (9) is supplemented with the relations

$$\rho = \rho(T, p); \quad C_p = C_p(T, p);$$

$j_r \ll j_z$. In this case, the term j^2/σ in equation (3), which describes the release of energy in the plasma due to the flow of electric current, will take the form j_z^2/σ . Within the framework of this approximation, the axial component of the electric field strength of the arc is practically constant over the cross section of the channel [7] and is determined from the condition of conservation of the total current:

$$I = 2\pi E_z \int_0^{R_\sigma(z)} \sigma r dr, \quad (6)$$

where $R_\sigma(z)$ is the radius of the conductive region. Considering that outside this region the plasma conductivity is practically zero, the radius of the calculation region can be used as the upper limit of integration in formula (6), i.e. set it equal to the channel radius $R_c(z)$, when integrating the system of equations (1) – (4) inside the working channel of the plasmatron, or equal to the radius of the external computational region R in an open arc.

The pressure distribution within the plasma-forming channel () is determined taking into account the magnetic component of pressure and gas swirl:

$$\chi = \chi(T, p); \quad \eta = \eta(T, p); \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma = \sigma(T, p); \quad \psi = \psi(T, p),$$

determining the dependence of thermodynamic characteristics, molecular transfer coefficients and optical properties of plasma on temperature and pressure. Detailed tables of the indicated values for the plasma-forming gases used are given, for example, in [7, 10].

The same system of gas-dynamic equations can also be used to describe the current-free (inertial) section of plasma flow, assuming $E_z = H_\phi = 0$. In the case where plasma flow is considered in plasma torches with an axial supply of plasma-forming gas, system of equations (1) – (4), as well as closing relations (7), (9) is simplified by taking $W = 0$.

Modeling of gas-dynamic and thermal characteristics of a plasma flow. Let us consider the results of calculations of the distributed characteristics of the plasma flow generated by a cutting plasmatron with reverse polarity. The calculated distributions of the temperature and plasma velocity along the length of the jet are presented in Fig. 2, and in Fig. 3 and 4 the radial distributions of temperature and the axial component of the air plasma velocity in characteristic sections of the computational region are shown.

Based on the presented results, the behavior of the plasma in the plasmatron under consideration, as well as in the open area and cutting cavity, can be represented as follows. The cold plasma-forming gas

entering the plasmatron through the annular channel $Z_1 \leq z \leq Z_2$ is gradually drawn into the flow. At the same time, in this section of the flow, the core of the plasma flow begins to form, but the annular near-wall flow of cold gas prevents the expansion of heated areas of the plasma, which is why a rather narrow current-conducting region is formed, the plasma temperature in which reaches values of 15...24 kK, at fairly low flow rates.

The further flow of plasma in the working channel of the plasma torch is associated with the expansion of the flow in the region $Z_2 \leq z \leq Z_3$, in which the core of the plasma flow expands and, accordingly, the temperature of the plasma on the axis drops. Then, turning into a confuser $Z_3 \leq z \leq Z_4$, the plasma flow is compressed, while the speed and temperature of the plasma increase significantly. At the entrance to the plasmatron output nozzle $Z_4 \leq z \leq 0$, the plasma flow almost completely fills the channel cross-section. Finding itself clamped by the relatively narrow walls of the plasmatron output nozzle, the flow is intensively accelerated and heated by an electric arc, reaching plasma

velocity and temperature values at the plasmatron nozzle exit of the order of 3000...7000 m/s and 16...18 kK, respectively.

Next, the plasma arc enters the open area $0 \leq z \leq Z_{c1}$. The outflow of plasma from the channel is always associated with an expansion of the plasma flow and a corresponding decrease in the plasma velocity and temperature. However, a significant decrease in the plasma velocity and temperature in the open area does not occur due to the relatively small open gap between the plasma torch nozzle exit and the surface of the product, as a result of which the plasma flow does not have time to disintegrate or expand significantly. In addition, the plasma in the flow continues to experience the action of electromagnetic forces, being in the area of action of the electric arc. Entering the cutting cavity, the plasma arc is clamped by its walls.

The flow in this section ($Z_{c1} \leq z \leq Z_{c2}$) is almost uniform: a slight drop in the axial plasma temperature is associated with the gradual filling of the cutting cavity with an arc, which leads to a partial redistribution of the plasma mass flow from the walls to the axis and a slight increase in the axial values of the plasma velocity.

Fig. 2. Distributions of axial values of plasma velocity (a) and temperature (b) along the jet axis: 1, 4, 5 – $I=350$ A, $G=6,42$ m³/h, 2 – $I=200$ A, $G=6,42$ m³/h, 3 – $I=350$ A, $G=8$ m³/h, 1-3 – $Re=2$ mm, $Z_{c1}=9$ mm, 4 – $Re=3$ mm, $Z_{c1}=9$ mm, 5 – $Re=2$ mm, $Z_{c1}=12$ mm.

The radial distributions of the axial velocity and plasma temperature in the areas corresponding to the plasmatron nozzle exit and near the surface of the cut product are presented in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. As can be seen, the gas-dynamic and thermal characteristics of the plasma are significantly dependent both on the parameters of the spraying mode, and on the geometric parameters of the plasma torch and the distance from the nozzle exit to the cut product. For example, using a nozzle of a larger diameter (see curve 4 in Fig.

2–4) at the same mass flow rate of plasma-forming gas leads to a significant decrease in plasma velocity. In addition, such a plasma flow has a larger core diameter, including when meeting the base of the cut product (see Fig. 4). With an increase in the distance separating the plasma torch nozzle section from the product, the speed and temperature of the plasma decrease slightly due to the longer time of interaction of the plasma flow with the environment and the expansion of the flow (see curve 5 in Fig. 2-4).

Fig. 3. Radial distributions of plasma velocity (a) and temperature (b) at the plasmatron nozzle exit ($z=0$): for designations, see Fig. 2.

Fig. 4. Radial distributions of plasma velocity (a) and temperature (b) near the surface of the cut product ($z=Z_{c1}$): see Fig. 2 for designations.

The pressure in the plasmatron under consideration drops noticeably (Fig. 5) only in the outlet nozzle ($Z_4 \leq z \leq 0$) and the confuser ($Z_3 \leq z \leq Z_4$), remaining practically constant, which is associated with the high gas-dynamic resistance of these sections of the working channel of the plasmatron.

Fig. 5. Plasma pressure distribution along the axis of the working channel of the cutting plasma torch: for symbols, see Fig. 2.

The dependences of the thermal and gas-dynamic characteristics of the plasma generated by the plasmatron under consideration (calculated in its output section, i.e. at $z = Z_3$), as well as the pressure drop along the entire length of the channel on the arc current, the flow rate of the plasma-forming gas and the geometric parameters of the plasmatron are shown in Fig. 6–10.

In particular, Fig. 6–10 shows the axial values of the plasma velocity and temperature, calculated in the output section of the plasmatron ($z=0$) and near the surface of the cut product ($z=Z_{c1}$), as well as the average mass temperature of the plasma in the output section of the plasmatron.

Fig. 6. Dependences of the axial velocity (a) and plasma temperature (b), as well as the pressure drop in the channel (c) on the arc current: 1 – output cross section of the plasmatron ($z=0$), 2 – near the surface of the product ($z=Z_{c1}$), 1' – mass-average plasma temperature in the output section of the plasmatron ($z=0$)

Fig. 7. Dependences of the axial velocity (a) and plasma temperature (b), as well as the pressure drop in the channel (c) on the flow rate of the plasma-forming gas (air): see Fig. 6 for designations.

As follows from the calculated data presented in these figures, the maximum value of the speed of the generated plasma flow, as well as the total pressure drop in the working channel of the plasma torch, increase with increasing arc current and the flow rate of the main plasma-forming gas (see Fig. 6, 7). As for the average mass temperature of the generated plasma, it increases with increasing I and decreases slightly with increasing G (see Fig. 6, b, 7, b). Note that in the open section of the flow the plasma flow expands, as a result of which the plasma velocity on the axis drops by

1000...2000 m/s (see curves 1, 2 in Fig. 6–10). At the same time, the change in plasma temperature on the axis in the open section of the arc (9 mm long) is not so noticeable. This may be due to the fact that as the flow expands, the plasma temperature at the periphery of the flow and, accordingly, its electrical conductivity decreases, which leads to an increase in the density of Joule energy sources, maintaining the plasma temperature at the initial stages of its movement in the open region to previously established values.

Fig. 8. Dependences of the axial velocity (a) and plasma temperature (b), as well as the pressure drop in the channel (c) on the radius of the output nozzle of the cutting plasma torch: for symbols, see Fig. 6.

The influence of the geometric parameters of the plasmatron output nozzle on the gas-dynamic and thermal characteristics of the plasma is illustrated in Figs. 8, 9. As can be seen, an increase in the radius of the output nozzle significantly affects the drop in plasma pressure in the working channel of the plasmatron: an increase in the transverse dimensions leads to a decrease in the gas-dynamic resistance of the

plasmatron output nozzle. The axial value of the axial velocity also drops significantly due to an increase in the transverse dimensions of the plasma flow. As the length of the output nozzle of the plasma torch increases (Fig. 9), the time of exposure of the arc to the plasma in the plasma torch channel and, consequently, the speed and temperature of the plasma at the exit from the plasma torch nozzle increases.

Fig. 9. Dependences of the axial velocity (a) and plasma temperature (b), as well as the pressure drop in the channel (c) on the length of the output nozzle of the cutting plasma torch: see Fig. 6 for designations.

Fig. 10. Dependences of the axial velocity (a) and plasma temperature (b) on the distance from the plasma torch nozzle to the surface of the product being cut: see Fig. 6 for symbols.

And finally, the influence of the open arc length on the gas-dynamic and thermal characteristics of the plasma generated by the cutting plasma torch is shown in Fig. 10. As can be seen, the values of plasma velocity and temperature are characterized by an almost linear decrease with increasing distance separating the output nozzle of the plasma torch from the surface of the part being cut.

Modeling the dimensions of the resulting cutting cavity. In plasma arc cutting, one of the most important characteristics of the process is the size of the resulting cutting cavity, in particular its depth and width. The combination of these parameters has a direct

impact on productivity, efficiency, quality of the metal cutting process and other factors. Within the framework of the created model, the depth of the cutting cavity is related to the thickness of the part being cut, and it is not possible to numerically study the movement of the reference spot of the arc into the depth of the cutting cavity. At the same time, it is possible to estimate the width of the resulting cut cavity, which is an equally important process parameter, since the width of the cut cavity largely determines the volume of melted metal and energy consumption. This makes it possible to select rational technological parameters for plasma-arc cutting, ensuring a reduction in energy and material

costs with other process quality indicators remaining unchanged.

Note that a correct assessment of the size of the melting area of the metal of a product is possible by constructing an appropriate model that takes into account both the body and force interaction of the plasma flow with the surface of the product being cut. At this stage, it is proposed to carry out a simplified assessment of the width of the cut cavity based on the radial profile of the plasma temperature near the surface of the product being cut (see Fig. 4,b): to assume the dimensions of the cut to be equal to the dimensions of

the plasma flow region, with plasma temperature values above a certain value. In particular, in the calculations, the temperature of 5000 K was chosen as the “boundary” temperature of the plasma, and the radius of the corresponding region was designated as r_T . The obtained results of assessing the dependence of the transverse dimensions of the cutting cavity on the parameters of the spraying mode and the geometric parameters of the plasmatron are summarized in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Change in the cross-sectional size of the cutting cavity depending on the arc current (a), the flow rate of the plasma-forming gas (b), the radius (c) and length (d) of the plasma torch output nozzle, as well as the length of the open section of the arc (e).

As can be seen from the presented results, the width of the resulting cut cavity ($2 \cdot r_T$) is 5.4...7.6 mm depending on the parameters of the plasma-arc cutting mode, which agrees quite well with the experimental data. The geometric parameters of the plasma torch have the greatest influence on the width of the cut. Thus, when the nozzle radius increases from 1.5 to 3 mm, the cross-sectional radius of the cutting cavity increases from 2.75 to 3.80 mm, which is ~38%. It is shown that, with other plasma cutting parameters remaining unchanged, an increase in operating current from 200 to 400 A leads to an increase in the width of the cut cavity by 12%, while an increase in the flow rate of plasma-forming air from 5 to 8 m³/h leads to a decrease in the transverse dimensions of the cut cavity by 6%. The average width of the cutting cavity is also slightly influenced by the length of the plasma torch output nozzle, changing which leads to changes in the width of the cutting cavity within 4...5%.

Conclusions.

1. A mathematical model of thermal, gas-dynamic and electromagnetic processes in electric arc plasma generated by cutting plasmatrons with reverse polarity is proposed. This model can be used to calculate the distributed and integral characteristics of the arc plasma flow generated by such plasma torches, both inside the working channel of the plasma torch and in the open area of the arc, as well as in the cutting cavity. At the same time, the model allows for numerical analysis in wide ranges of arc current and plasma gas flow rate, as well as geometric parameters of the plasma torch working channel, external region and cutting cavity.

2. It has been established that the distributed and integral characteristics of the cutting arc plasma generated by the plasma torch at reverse polarity are significantly influenced by the radius of the plasma torch output nozzle (1.5–3.0 mm), the thickness of the cut product (15–70 mm), as well as the mode parameters plasma torch operation (current 200–400 A and gas flow 5–8 m³/h).

3. The transverse dimensions of the cutting cavity lie in the range of 5.4–7.6 mm and are almost directly proportional to the distance separating the plasma torch cut from the surface of the product being cut (8–12 mm), as well as the radius of the plasma torch output nozzle (1.5–3.0 mm) and parameters of its operating mode (current strength 200–400 A and gas flow 5–8 m³/h).

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